

VIDEO SCALABILITY RATE CONTROL METHOD BY DYNAMIC CONTROLLING OF BITS ALLOCATION RATIO

Hiroyuki KASAI[†], Mei KODAMA^{††} and Hideyoshi TOMINAGA[†]

[†] Waseda University: 1-3-10 Nishi-Waseda, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo, 169-0051, JAPAN

^{††} Hiroshima University: 3-10-31 Kagamiyama, Higashi-Hiroshima, Hiroshima 739-0046, JAPAN
e-mail: kasai@giti.waseda.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

This paper proposes the new coding rate control method in MPEG-2 video scalability. First of all, we investigate the efficiency of SNR scalability from the relations between hierarchical allocated bits and picture quality. Next, base on the the efficiency, we propose the new coding rate control method which has the dynamic controlling of bits allocation ratio. From the simulation experiments, we show the effectiveness in comparison to MPEG-2 TM5 rate control method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hierarchical image coding method, such as MPEG-2 scalability[1] are very important in the advanced video providing services. Hierarchical image coding method have the various functions which are image quality selection and the error resilience, and so on. But, since the thorough investigation of hierarchical loss is not enough, the relation bits allocation ratio and image quality is not clear. Moreover, the rate control method peculiar to the hierarchical coding is not clear too. So, the non-hierarchical rate control methods are used for the hierarchical coding under the present conditions. In particular, hierarchical loss caused by the traditional rate control method are the largest problems.

In this paper, we propose the new coding rate control method in MPEG-2 video scalability which controls the bit allocation ratio dynamically. This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we show the hierarchical loss caused by the traditional rate control method(MPEG-2 Test Model 5[2]) from simulation experiment. In Section 3 we propose the the new coding rate control method in MPEG-2 video scalability. In Section 4 we show the effectiveness in comparison to MPEG-2 TM5. Finally we summarize our major findings. In this paper, we focus on the SNR scalability in MPEG-2.

2 HIERARCHICAL LOSS

2.1 TM5 Rate Control Method

In Step 1 of TM5, target bits $T^{ipb}(l, h)$ for each pictures, I,P,B-picture, are calculated by the equation (1).

$$\begin{cases} T^i(l, h) = R(l, h) / \{ N_i + \alpha(l, h) + \beta(l, h) \} \\ T^p(l, h) = R(l, h) / \{ N_p + \gamma(l, h) \} \\ T^b(l, h) = R(l, h) / \{ N_b + \delta(l, h) \} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In equation(1), N_i , N_p and N_b are the number of I-, P- and B-picture before encoding in current GOP. α , β , γ and δ are the number of current picture converted from each picture before coding. α , β , γ and δ are calculated base on the bits allocation ratio $br\%(l, h)$. The most important point of the TM5 rate control is that the bits allocation ratio $br\%(l, h)$ is constant in all pictures.

2.2 Simulation Experiments

We show the relation between the bit allocation ratio and picture quality from simulation results. Simulation experiment conditions are that coding rate is 9[Mbps], test sequence are Mobile&Calendar, Flower Garden and Table Tennis, and the target coding allocated ratio, which is called ρ_T , are from 0.0 to 1.0. The relation between ρ_T and Signal to Noise Ratio(SNR) in enhancement layer are showed in the Fig. (1).

Figure 1: ρ_T and enhancement-layer SNR

From Fig. (1), we understand that picture quality is worst in the middle ρ_T .

2.3 TM5 Characteristics

From 2.2, we investigate TM5 coding characteristics. First of all, we show the hierarchical loss function $D(\rho)$

which represents the relation between ρ_T and the hierarchical loss in comparison with the non-hierarchical coding (Fig. (2)). From Fig. (2), the each function $D(\rho)$

Figure 2: Hierarchical loss function $D(\rho)$

in each picture is approximated to two dimensional functions $\varphi_i(\rho)$, $\varphi_p(\rho)$ and $\varphi_b(\rho)$. And we define the minimal value of $\varphi_i(\rho)$, $\varphi_p(\rho)$ and $\varphi_b(\rho)$ as ρ_o^i , ρ_o^p and ρ_o^b .

From $\varphi_i(\rho)$, $\varphi_p(\rho)$ and $\varphi_b(\rho)$, we define the characteristics function $E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b)$ in equation(2). In equation(2), N_{i_o} , N_{p_o} and N_{b_o} are the number of the picture in GOP, and $N_{i_o} = 1, N_{p_o} = N/M - 1$ and $N_{b_o} = N - N/M$ are valid.

$$E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b) = N_{i_o} \varphi_i(\rho^i) + N_{p_o} \varphi_p(\rho^p) + N_{b_o} \varphi_b(\rho^b) \quad (2)$$

In the TM5, $E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b)$ is valid in equation(3). In this way, we understand that the TM5 control method causes the hierarchical loss showed in equation(3).

$$E(\rho_T, \rho_T, \rho_T) = N_{i_o} \varphi_i(\rho_T) + N_{p_o} \varphi_p(\rho_T) + N_{b_o} \varphi_b(\rho_T) \quad (3)$$

3 PROPOSED CONTROL METHOD

3.1 Overview

We propose the hierarchical rate control method which provides the best quality based on the inputted ρ_T , considering the hierarchical loss. Proposed method is based on the $\varphi_i(\rho)$, $\varphi_p(\rho)$ and $\varphi_b(\rho)$. The most important point is that proposed method controls bits allocation ratio dynamically in each picture. In the concrete, this method is organized as follows.

- (1) Update ρ_T to ρ^i, ρ^p, ρ^b

In I- or P-picture, ρ_T is updated to ρ^i and ρ^p which are larger than ρ_T . Whereas in B-picture, ρ_T is updated to ρ^b which is smaller than ρ_T .

- (2) Restrictive condition to base-layer bits

When ρ_T is updated to ρ^{ipb} , the ratio of base-layer bits to total bits must be constant ρ_T . Then, in base-layer, we define coding bits saved in B-picture in the past as R_{past}^- , coding bits saved in the future as R_{pre}^- , coding bits spent in I or P-picture in the past as R_{past}^+ , coding bits spent in the future as R_{pre}^+ . From these parameters, the restrictive condition $G(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b) = 0$ is found in equation(4).

$$G(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b) = R_{pre}^+ + R_{past}^+ + R_{pre}^- + R_{past}^- = 0 \quad (4)$$

- (3) Most suitable ρ_{I}^{ipb} under restrictive condition

Under restrictive condition, proposed method calculates the most suitable $\rho_I^i, \rho_I^p, \rho_I^b$ which provides the largest $E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b)$ value.

3.2 Proposed Rate Control Method

We explain the calculation method for $\rho_I^i, \rho_I^p, \rho_I^b$ in each picture.

3.2.1 I-Picture

Since in I-picture, coded picture is not existing, R_{past}^+ and R_{pre}^- are zero. So, R_{pre}^+ and R_{pre}^- is indicated in equation(5) and (6) respectively.

$$R_{pre}^+ = T^i (\rho^i - \rho_T) + T^i \alpha (\rho^p - \rho_T) \quad (5)$$

$$R_{pre}^- = T^i \beta (\rho_T - \rho^b) \quad (6)$$

From (5) and (6), under restrictive condition equation (4), we calculate the largest $E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b)$ value. This calculation is formulated as the maximum problem of E . So we calculate the problem by Lagrange equation. Here, in equation(7) we show the condition ($\rho_{max}^i, \rho_{max}^p, \rho_{min}^b$) for the range of (ρ^i, ρ^p, ρ^b). In equation(7), $R_{min}(l, h)$ is the necessary minimum coding bits in each layer.

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{max}^i = \{ T^i - R_{min}(h) \} / T^i \\ \rho_{max}^p = \{ T^i \alpha - R_{min}(h) N_p \} / (T^i \alpha) \\ \rho_{min}^b = R_{min}(l) N_b / (T^i \beta) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Based on the above mentioned, Lagrange equation showed in equation(8) is calculated.

$$J_i = E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b) - \lambda_i G(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b) \quad (8)$$

From equation(8), when $\partial J_i / \partial \rho^i = \partial J_i / \partial \rho^p = \partial J_i / \partial \rho^b = \partial J_i / \partial \lambda_i = 0$ is valid, relative value ρ_{rel}^i is calculated by equation(9).

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{rel}^i = 2 C_1 N_b g (1 + \alpha) (1 + \alpha + \beta) \rho_T - \\ C_1 \{ \beta^2 (b + N_p e) - \beta h N_b (1 + \alpha) \} \\ C_1 = \frac{1}{2 \{ g N_b (1 + \alpha)^2 - \beta^2 (a + N_p d) \}} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

From equation(9), we can understand that ρ_{rel}^i indicates the minimal value in $E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b)$. So we consider base on the following three cases.

Case (1) $\rho_T \geq \rho_{rel}^i$

Since E is monotonous increase in the range of ρ , $\rho^i = \rho_{max}^i$ is prospective value. So, ρ^b in this case is calculated in equation(10).

$$\rho^b = \frac{(1 + \alpha + \beta) \rho_T - (1 + \alpha) \rho_{max}^i}{\beta} \quad (10)$$

Here, we study base on the two cases moreover.

$$(1) \rho^b \geq \rho_{min}^b \iff \rho_T \geq \rho_{th}^i$$

Here, ρ_{th}^i is showed in equation(11).

$$\rho_{th}^i = \frac{T^i + T^i\alpha + R_m(l)N_b - R_m(h)(1 + \alpha)}{T^i(1 + \alpha + \beta)} \quad (11)$$

In this case, $\rho^i = \rho_{max}^i$ is fixed.

$$(2) \rho^b < \rho_{min}^b \iff \rho_T < \rho_{th}^i$$

In this case, $\rho^b = \rho_{min}^b$ is fixed.

Case (2) $\rho_T \leq \rho_{rel}^i \leq \rho_{max}^p$

$\rho^i = \rho_{max}^i$, ρ_T is prospective value. But in the case of $\rho^i = \rho_T$, the bits allocation ratio is not updated. So this case is not suitable. From this, $\rho^i = \rho_{max}^i$ is prospective value. This case is equal to the Case (1).

Case (3) $\rho_{max}^i \leq \rho_{rel}^i$

Since E is monotonous decrease in the range of ρ , $\rho^i = \rho_T$ is prospective value. But, because bits ratio is not updated in this case, this case is not suitable.

From Case (1)–(3), $E(\rho^i, \rho^p, \rho^b)$ indicates the largest value in the case that ρ^i satisfy equation(12).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{(I)} \rho_T < \rho_{th}^i \\ \rho_I^i = \frac{(1 + \alpha + \beta) \rho_T - \beta \rho_{min}^b}{1 + \alpha} \\ \text{(II)} \rho_{th}^i \leq \rho_T \\ \rho_I^i = \rho_{max}^i \end{array} \right. \quad (12)$$

3.2.2 P-Picture

R_{past}^+ , R_{past}^- , R_{pre}^+ , R_{pre}^- are indicated in equation(13), (14), (15) and (16) respectively.

$$R_{past}^+ = \{T_R^i(l) - T^i \rho_T\} + \sum_{N_p^i} \{T_R^p(l) - T^p \rho_T\} \quad (13)$$

$$R_{past}^- = \sum_{N_b^i} \{T^b \rho_T - T_R^b(l)\} \quad (14)$$

$$R_{pre}^+ = T^p N_p (\rho^p - \rho_T) \quad (15)$$

$$R_{pre}^- = T^p \gamma (\rho_T - \rho^b) \quad (16)$$

Here, in equation(17) we show the condition $(\rho_{max}^p, \rho_{min}^b)$ for the range of (ρ^p, ρ^b) .

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho_{max}^p = \{T^p - R_m(h)\} / T^p \\ \rho_{min}^b = R_m(l) / (T^p \gamma) \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

As I-picture, we calculate ρ_I^p . Calculated ρ_I^p is showed in equation(18).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{(I)} \rho_T < \rho_{th}^p \\ \rho_I^p = \frac{(N_p + \gamma) \rho_T - \gamma \rho_{min}^b}{N_p} + \frac{R_{past}^- - R_{past}^+}{T^p N_p} \\ \text{(II)} \rho_{th}^p \leq \rho_T \\ \rho_I^p = \rho_{max}^p \end{array} \right. \quad (18)$$

Here, ρ_{th}^p is showed in equation(19).

$$\rho_{th}^p = \frac{T^p N_b - R_m(h)N_p + R_m(l)N_b + R_{past}^+ - R_{past}^-}{T^p (N_p + \gamma)} \quad (19)$$

3.2.3 B-Picture

R_{past}^+ is equal to equation(13) and R_{past}^- is equal to equation(14). So R_{pre}^+ , R_{pre}^- are indicated in equation(20) and (21) respectively.

$$R_{pre}^+ = T^b \delta (\rho^p - \rho_T) \quad (20)$$

$$R_{pre}^- = T^b N_b (\rho_T - \rho^b) \quad (21)$$

Here, in equation(22) we show the condition $(\rho_{max}^p, \rho_{min}^b)$ for the range of (ρ^p, ρ^b) .

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho_{max}^p = \{T^b \delta - R_m(h)N_p\} / (T^b \delta) \\ \rho_{min}^b = R_m(l) / T^b \end{array} \right. \quad (22)$$

As I- and P-picture, we calculate ρ_I^b . Calculated ρ_I^b is showed in equation(23).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{(I)} \rho_T < \rho_{th}^b \\ \rho_I^b = \rho_{min}^b \\ \text{(II)} \rho_{th}^b \leq \rho_T \\ \rho_I^b = \frac{(N_b + \delta) \rho_T - \delta \rho_{max}^p}{N_b} - \frac{R_{past}^- - R_{past}^+}{T^b N_b} \end{array} \right. \quad (23)$$

Here, ρ_{th}^b is showed in equation(24).

$$\rho_{th}^b = \frac{T^b \delta - R_m(h)N_p + R_m(l)N_b + R_{past}^+ - R_{past}^-}{T^b (\delta + N_p)} \quad (24)$$

4 EVALUATION

Simulation experiments purpose to evaluate the effectiveness of proposed method. The experiment condition is similar to that of 2.2. And $R_m(l, h)$ is 20000, each coefficient $(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)$ of $\varphi_i(\rho)$, $\varphi_p(\rho)$, $\varphi_b(\rho)$ is $(3.9, -4.9, 2.0, 1.5, -1.8, 1.3, 0.9, -1.1, 1.2)$.

4.1 Changes of ρ

The changes of ρ is showed in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Changes of ρ ($\rho_T = 0.51$)

From Fig. 3, we understand the larger changes of ρ in comparison with TM5 method. ρ indicates larger value in I-P-picture, and ρ indicates smaller value in B-picture.

4.2 Changes of SNR

The changes of SNR in each ρ of Mobile&Calendar are showed in Fig. 4. And, the relation between SNR, and coding bits in each layer in $R_T = 0.60$, which is the worst case in Section 2, is showed in Table 1. Moreover, the same relation in non-hierarchical coding (MPEG-2 MP@ML) is showed in Table 2.

Figure 4: ρ_T and enhancement layer SNR (Mobile&Calendar)

From Fig. 4, we understand that the proposed method can remove the hierarchical loss.

Table 1: SNR and coding bits ($\rho_T = 0.60$) (MPEG-2 TM5 Method and Proposed Method)

Method		MPEG-2 TM5			Proposed		
Sequence		mobl	flow	tabl	mobl	flow	tabl
5.4	Y	28.02	29.36	30.58	28.64	29.68	31.32
	Cb	34.10	32.97	40.72	35.15	33.86	41.28
	Cr	34.15	34.92	40.19	35.12	35.63	40.49
Base		5.408	5.414	5.404	5.406	5.358	5.431
3.6	Y	31.67	33.24	33.30	32.41	33.87	33.80
	Cb	36.57	35.80	42.02	37.20	36.28	42.26
	Cr	36.78	36.80	41.63	37.42	37.20	41.93
Enha.		3.592	3.588	3.596	3.594	3.648	3.575
Total		9.001	9.002	9.001	9.000	9.006	9.006

Table 2: SNR and coding bits (Non-Hierarchical Coding)

Sequence	mobl	flow	tabl
Y	32.51	34.11	34.22
Cb	37.32	36.53	42.61
Cr	37.56	37.43	42.32
Total	8.998	9.000	9.000

From Table 1, though coding bits is same in each layer and total, the proposed method can restrain the hierarchical loss in comparison with TM5 method. When we make a comparison between Table 1 and Table 2, the decrease of SNR caused by hierarchical loss in TM5 method is 0.84[dB]. Whereas the decrease in proposed method is 0.1[dB].

Moreover we show the changes of SNR in each picture in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. From Fig. 5 and Fig.6, we understand that the proposed method is superior to TM5 method in each picture.

Figure 5: Changes of SNR in each picture (Mobile&Calendar)

Figure 6: Changes of SNR in each picture (Flower Garden)

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed the new coding rate control method in MPEG-2 video scalability. First of all, we show that picture quality is worst in the middle ρ_T . Next, based on the efficiency, we state the new coding rate control method which has the dynamic controlling of bits allocation ratio. From the simulation experiments, we showed the effectiveness in comparison to MPEG-2 TM5 rate control method.

References

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